

ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES OF SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART V.

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The adsorption of inorganic acids, bases and salts by various resins has been studied. The acids are adsorbed in the order $\text{HI} > \text{HCl} > \text{HBr}$; $\text{HNO}_3 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$, and $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4 > \text{HClO}_4 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$, and bases $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$; $\text{KOH} > \text{NaOH} > \text{LiOH} > \text{NH}_4\text{OH}$. In the case of salts the order of adsorption of cations is $\text{Rb} > \text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$ and in anions $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$. The acid-condensed phenolic resin does not adsorb the acids and salts. The order of sorption is explained on the basis of the polar concept.

Sato and Sekine (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1921, **24**, 51) and Shono (*ibid.*, 1926, **29**, 53) were the first to show the amphoteric nature of phenol-formaldehyde resins. Adam and Holms (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, **54**, 111) concluded that the positive ion was more adsorbed as hydroxide or carbonate. Bhatnagar, Kapur and Puri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 679) found that the acids were adsorbed in the order: $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{HNO}_3 > \text{HCl}$ and the bases $\text{KOH} > \text{NaOH} > \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 > \text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3$. Akeroyed and Broughton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, **42**, 3437) had shown that in acid-condensed phenolic resin the alkalis are adsorbed in the order: $\text{NaOH} > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$. Broughton and Lee (*ibid.*, 1939, **43**, 737) had shown that in aromatic amine-formaldehyde resin HCl is more adsorbed than H_2SO_4 .

Dubinen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **140A**, 81; 1930, **150A**, 145) had shown that charcoal, heated to 550° , adsorbed acids in the order: $\text{HCl} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$, while heated to 800° , this order was reversed. Bartell and Fu (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 676) had shown that the polar silica adsorbed alkali in the order: $\text{LiOH} > \text{NaOH} > \text{KOH} > \text{NH}_4\text{OH}$, but it did not adsorb strong acids.

In most of the above cases no effort had been made to explain a particular order. The present work deals with the adsorption of inorganic acids, bases and salts and an attempt has been made to explain the adsorption on the concept of the polar nature of sorbate, the solvent and the resin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The adsorption experiments were carried out with the resin prepared in the same way as in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*),

TABLE I.

Acids.	Titrated against.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.			Protein resin.
		HCl-condensed.	NH ₃ -condensed.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine resin.	
Hydrochloric	NaOH	0·0	24·6	66·0	28·4
	AgNO ₃	0·0	25·0	66·60	29·2
Formic	NaOH	3·3	20·04	33·65	3·3
	KMnO ₄	3·15	19·80	32·80	3·2
Oxalic	NaOH	1·75	34·60	74·40	25·0
	KMnO ₄	1·60	33·85	73·50	24·6

In Table I, the estimation of acids has been carried out by two different methods, *i.e.*, either estimation of H⁺ ion by means of NaOH or of the Cl⁻ ion by AgNO₃ or of the whole molecule by KMnO₄ titrations. The agreement between the two results definitely establishes the nature of the adsorption to be molecular and not ionic in character.

The existence of undissociated molecules appears also to be supported by the refractometric investigations of Fajans. For most of the numerous electrolytes which Heydweiller (*Physikal. Z.*, 1925, 26, 529) investigated, he was not able to detect any variation of refractivity with concentration in dilute solution. The refractivity is defined as the value per mole of the Lorenz-Lorentz expression,

$$R = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{G}{d} = \frac{4\pi}{3} N \alpha_e.$$

When n is the refractive index, G , the molecular weight, d , the density, N , Loschmidt's number and α_e , the polarisability of the molecule, which is the measure of the deformability of the electron shells by an electric field. Van Vleck has come to the same conclusions for gases on the basis of the new quantum mechanics. Hence the refractivity or the molar refraction is directly proportional to the polarisability of the molecule in solution.

In the previous paper (Part IV) it had already been shown that the basic resins are more polar than water, while the acid-condensed phenolic resins are less polar. In the case of basic resins at the resin-water interface, the molecule of the sorbate will orient itself in such a way that the polar group is oriented towards the resin, while the non-polar group is oriented towards water. The reverse will be the condition in acid-condensed phenolic resins. The greater the polarisability of the molecule in solution, the greater will be its adsorption. As the polarisability

increases with molar refraction, the adsorption will also increase with the molar refraction. Therefore, in basic resins, the greater the molar refraction of the sorbate in solution, the greater will be the adsorption. The reverse will hold good in the case of acid-condensed phenolic resins.

TABLE II.

% Sorption of halogens by 1 g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 M aq. solution.

Halogens	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin.		<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine resin.	Protein resin.	Molar refraction.
	HCl-condensed.	NH ₂ -condensed			
Chlorine	8.7	5.8	46.4	21.7	11.67
Bromine	2.0	8.0	52.0	28.0	17.43
Iodine in KI soln.	62.0	95.00	99.0	90.0	31.97

The values for molar refraction are taken from Smyth ("Dielectric Constant and Molecular Structure").

It can be seen from Table II that the adsorption of the halogens increases with the molar refraction in the case of basic resins, while it decreases in acid-condensed phenolic resin except iodine. The adsorption of iodine is abnormal practically in all the cases. Probably it may be due to its nature of forming complexes with potassium iodide.

TABLE III.

% Sorption of halogen acids by 1 g. of basic resins from 100 c.c. of their 0.01M-aq. solution.

Acids.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin (NH ₂ -condensed).	<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine resin.	Protein resin.	Molar refraction.
HCl	25.0	66.6	29.2	6.68
HBr	14.6	48.0	20.85	9.14
HI	27.3	87.3	36.6	13.75

The halogen acids are not adsorbed by acid-condensed phenolic resin was expected.

It can be seen from Table III that the sorption of halogen acids also increases with the molar refraction except hydrobromic acid. It is well known that dissociation of HBr is too much, hence it may be expected to be least adsorbed.

It has been shown by Falkenhagen ("Electrolytes," translated by K. P. Bell, Clarendon Press, 1934 p. 319) that in aqueous solutions the free hydrated H^+ ion causes negative refractivity of +0.6 unit. The refractivity of the acids will depend on the refractivity of the anion. Therefore, in the case of acids the adsorption will also depend on the refractivity of the anion.

TABLE IV.
% Sorption of acids by 1g. of basic resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 *M*-aq. solutions.

Acids.	Resorcinol resin NH ₂ -condensed.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine resin.	Protein resin	Refraction* for the complex ions.	Com- plex ion
HNO ₃	32.72	73.0	32.72	11.0	NO ₃
H ₂ SO ₃	24.6	65.2	24.2	5.5	$\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₃
H ₃ BO ₃	4.67	5.13	4.2	<5.5	$\frac{1}{3}$ BO ₃

* The values for the refraction of complex ions have been taken from "Dielectric Constant and Molecular Structure" by Smyth (*loc. cit.*).

It can be seen from Table IV that as the refraction of the complex ions increases, the adsorption also increases. Although no definite value for the BO₃ ion is given, it has been shown that the ionic refraction of S is 15, while that of B is 0.05. Hence it is assumed that the value for BO₃ ion would be much less than SO₃.

TABLE V.
% Sorption of acids by 1g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 *M*-aq. solutions.

Acids.	Resorcinol resin NH ₂ -condensed.	<i>m</i> -Phenylene diamine resin.	Protein resin.	Refraction for the complex ion.	Com- plex ions.
HClO ₄	33.48	81.48	35.2	13.32	ClO ₄
H ₂ SO ₄	30.0	70.0	24.8	7.31	$\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₄
H ₃ PO ₄	22.2	55.5	20.0	5.43	$\frac{1}{3}$ PO ₄
H ₂ CrO ₄	96.0	98.3	75.83	>13.32	$\frac{1}{2}$ CrO ₄

In Table V also the adsorption increases with the refraction of the complex ions. The refraction of the chromate ion was not determined because of its uncertainty due to proximity to an absorption band. Hence no definite value is given to it. The order of sorption of acids is HI > HCl > HBr, HNO₃ > H₂SO₃ > H₃BO₃ and H₂CrO₄ > HClO₄ > H₂SO₄ > H₃PO₄.

TABLE VI.

% Sorption of alkali halides by 1g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 M-aq. solution.

Cation.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin (NH ₃ -condensed)			<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine resin			Protein resin.		
	Cl.	Br.	I.	Cl.	Br.	I.	Cl.	Br.	I.
Li	0.0	1.00	2.50	0.92	3.14	5.48	0.46	1.85	3.8
Na	0.47	1.90	2.80	1.88	4.25	5.74	0.94	2.5	4.2
K	0.93	2.10	3.0	2.77	5.10	6.25	1.25	2.7	4.6
Rb	1.85	2.30	3.2	3.7	5.30	6.70	2.00	3.0	5.0

TABLE VII.

Molar refractions (NaD line) of alkali halides at infinite dilution.

Cation.	Cl.	Br.	I.
Li	8.58	12.25	18.82
Na	9.2	12.87	19.44
K	11.23	14.90	21.47
Rb	12.58	16.25	22.82

* The values are taken from "Dielectric Constant and Molecular Structure", by Smyth, p. 145.

It can be seen from Tables VI and VII that the adsorption increases with the molar refraction. The order of sorption of cations is Rb > K > Na > Li and of anion is I > Br > Cl.

The acid-condensed phenolic resin did not adsorb the acids and the salts.

TABLE VIII.

% Sorption of alkalis by 1g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 M-aqueous solutions.

Alkalis.	Resorcinol-formaldehyde resin		Refractive index.	Molar refraction.
	HCl-condensed.	NH ₃ -condensed.		
LiOH	91.45	83.67	1.3375	3.11
NaOH	92.53	86.34	1.3380	3.915
KOH	94.32	88.27	1.3427	5.803
NH ₄ OH	70.36	52.86	1.3326	

It can be seen from Table VIII that the adsorption of alkalis also increases with the molar refraction. The adsorption of ammonia is the least. Although its molar refraction is not yet known it can be seen from the refractive indices that its adsorption should be the least.

TABLE IX.

% Sorption of alkalis by 1g. of resin from 100 c.c. of their 0.01 *M*-aq. solutions.

Alkalis.	Resorcinol formaldehyde resin			Molar refraction.
	HCl-condensed.	NH ₃ -condensed.	Protein resin.	
Ca(OH) ₂	98.45	90.81	56.12	8.425
Sr(OH) ₂	99.00	91.66	57.02	39.44
Ba(OH) ₂	99.57	93.68	59.69	43.68

Table IX shows the adsorption of Ca(OH)₂, Ba(OH)₂, Sr(OH)₂. Here too the adsorption increases with the molar refraction.

So it can be seen from all the above results that the adsorption increases with the molar refraction. The results fully corroborate the polar concept discussed in our previous paper.

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